

Consent form for the Images for the PROTEST-AIRT project

Marie Skłodowska-Curie Postdoctoral Fellowship (Grant Agreement 101057156)

I hereby consent to and authorize the University of Potsdam, a non-profit academic institution, to use any images depicting my person for the PROTEST-AIRT project. This project analyses the emerging dissent against air transport in Europe and the images could be used for both academic and communication purposes (for example, in public lectures, media or the official website of the project).

I consent to the use of images depicting my person in the following cases:

- Journals and scientific publications

YES	NO
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- The PROTEST-AIRT website (hosted at the University of Potsdam)

YES	NO
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- Activities of communication of findings (conferences or public lectures)

YES	NO
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- Press releases (for wider audiences in television, newspapers and other media)

YES	NO
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I consent to the deposition of these images in a public repository as part of the open data linked to the PROTEST-AIRT project. After this publication, the images will be available to anyone, free of costs.

YES	NO
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I am aware that these images include my participation in an act of political dissent and waive any rights regarding any future compensation for the use of these images. I also release the University of Potsdam from any legal responsibility concerning risks or harms to my person originating from the use of these images or its deposition in a public repository.

I authorize Dr Alexander Araya López, the researcher in charge of the PROTEST-AIRT project, to create, store, process and publish these images of my person for the aforementioned uses.

- You must be 18 years of age or older to take part in this research study.
- You will be given a copy of this consent form for your records.

Name:

Address:

Email:

Date:

Signature:

Dr Alexander ARAYA LÓPEZ
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